

TENSILE PROPERTIES OF Al_2O_3 PARTICULATE REINFORCED 6061Al COMPOSITE AT LIQUID NITROGEN TEMPERATURE

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ABSTRACT

Tensile properties of a 6061Al/ Al_2O_3 particulate composite tempered to different aging conditions were determined as a function of testing temperature. With lowering testing temperature from room to liquid nitrogen temperature, the naturally aged specimens showed an obviously improved yield strength and a slightly reduced elongation, the artificially aged specimens exhibited an improved yield strength and an enhanced ductility. Examination of the deformation and fracture characteristics with scanning electron microscope revealed no essential differences between the specimens tested at room and liquid nitrogen temperatures. Based upon the results obtained, mechanisms responsible for the cryogenic mechanical behavior of the 6061Al/ Al_2O_3 composite were deduced.

INTRODUCTION

Not much attention has been paid to the cryogenic mechanical behavior of discontinuously reinforced aluminum matrix composites. The very limited results in the literature however showed some quite interesting points, when the composites were deformed at liquid nitrogen temperature. For example, Hong and Gray [1] found that the compressive flow stress and strain hardening capacity of a 1060Al/ Al_2O_3 composite at 77K are much higher than those at room temperature, while Ma et al [2] reported that both their 2124Al/SiCw and 2124Al/SiCp composites produced through a powder metallurgy method exhibited obviously improved cryogenic ultimate tensile stresses. Even so, there is a dearth of experimental data related to the cryogenic mechanical behavior of discontinuously reinforced aluminum matrix composite, the underlying mechanisms are not yet clearly addressed.

To acquire a better understanding of the cryogenic mechanical behavior of discontinuously reinforced aluminum matrix composites, an investigation was performed in the present study to evaluate the tensile properties of a 6061Al/ Al_2O_3 particulate composite at both liquid nitrogen

and room temperatures. By comparing the results so obtained, some insight into the low temperature-related mechanical behavior was deduced.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The material used in this study was a 6061Al matrix composite, reinforced with 20 volume percent Al_2O_3 particles (average size = 15 μm), in the form of 19 mm diameter extruded bar. The composite was acquired from Duralcan and was produced by a molten metal method. Nominal chemical compositions of the 6061Al matrix are (0.8-1.2)Mg, (0.4-0.8)Si, 0.7Fe, (0.15-0.40)Cu, 0.25Zn, 0.15Mn and 0.04Cr in weight percent, balanced by Al.

After subjected to a solid solution treatment at 525°C for 2 hours and a room temperature water quench, blanks of the rod were machined into tensile specimens of 6.35 mm gauge diameter and of 25.4 mm gauge length. The specimens were then divided into three groups according to the aging procedures they subsequently received. These aging conditions were (i) naturally aged for 10 days (NA), (ii) artificially aged at 175°C for 8 hours (T6) and (iii) artificially aged at 175°C for 48 hours (PA). Before any testing, portions of gauge length of the tensile specimens were mechanically polished with 320 grit sand papers.

Tensile tests were conducted with an Instron machine at a nominal strain rate of $3 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$, at both room and liquid nitrogen temperatures. Load-elongation curves were recorded with an X-Y recorder. Tensile tests at the cryogenic temperature were carried out after each specimen had been immersed into liquid nitrogen for at least 15 minutes.

Surfaces of the deformed and fractured specimens were examined with scanning electron microscopy (SEM), to characterize the deformation and fracture features of the composite.

RESULTS

1. PROPERTIES

Tensile properties of the 6061Al/ Al_2O_3 composite are listed in Table 1. It is apparent that at both room and liquid nitrogen temperatures, the strength levels were improved with aging, while the ductility was reduced. It should also be noticed that most of the property changes were completed at the early stage of aging. After aging at 175°C for 8 hours, property variations with further increasing aging time became quite mild.

In comparing the strength levels of the composite specimens measured at the two temperatures, much higher values were obtained at liquid nitrogen temperature than at room temperature. For NA, T6 and PA conditions, the increments in the yield strength (YS, 0.2% proof stress) were 73%, 15% and 13% respectively. The ultimate tensile stresses (UTSs) of the naturally and artificially aged specimens increased approximately the same percentage (14%-16%).

Ductility at liquid nitrogen temperature showed some complexity. The NA specimens exhibited a little poorer cryogenic elongation, while the artificially aged specimens exhibited a higher elongation than those tested at room temperature. The increase in elongation along with an increase in strength with lowering testing temperature is an unusual phenomenon.

Table 1 Tensile Properties of the Composite at Room (RT) and Liquid Nitrogen (LN) Temperatures

Condition	YS, MPa		UTS, MPa		Elongation, %	
	RT	LN	RT	LN	RT	LN
NA	128	221	269	313	9.2	8.7
T6	305	352	326	379	4.3	6.2
PA	311	351	334	382	3.5	5.9

2. DEFORMATION BEHAVIOR

Highly localized conjugate strain bands were observed with SEM on the deformed specimen surfaces (Fig.1a). Microcracks were found to initiate at individual broken Al_2O_3 particles (Fig.1b), and then grow along, or link with each other through, the localized strain bands (Fig.1c).

(a) PA, room temperature

(b) NA, room temperature

(c) NA, liquid nitrogen temperature

Fig.1 SEM micrographs of the deformed specimen surfaces showing (a) localized conjugate strain bands, (b) a microcrack nucleated at a broken Al_2O_3 particulate, and (c) microcracks grew along, or linked with each other through, the localized strain bands

3. FRACTURE CHARACTERISTICS

Regardless of testing temperature and aging condition, the composite exhibited essentially identical fracture features manifested by large voids with broken Al_2O_3 particles at the bottoms and tear failure ridges of the matrix between adjacent reinforcements (Fig.2). There were also some smaller dimples on the tear failure ridges, which became increasingly appreciable with aging at room temperature or with lowering testing temperature for a given condition. Hardly any interfacial cracks between the 6061Al matrix and the Al_2O_3 reinforcement could be identified even when the fracture surfaces were closely examined.

(a) NA, room temperature

(b) T6, room temperature

(c) T6, liquid nitrogen temperature

Fig.2 SEM micrographs of the fracture surfaces showing large voids containing broken Al_2O_3 particles and tear failure ridges of the matrix between adjacent reinforcements. Note that nearly every void has a broken Al_2O_3 particle at its bottom and few interfacial cracks are visible. Note also the increasingly appreciable smaller dimples on the tear failure ridges, with aging or with lowering testing temperature.

DISCUSSIONS

Since there are no essential differences in the deformation and fracture characteristics between the composite specimens tested at room and liquid nitrogen temperatures, they cannot provide any information on where the improvement in the cryogenic properties was derived from. It is, however, convinced by the SEM observations that the matrix-particulate interfaces still remained to be well-bonded even when the composite was deformed at liquid nitrogen temperature.

In a particulate reinforced aluminum matrix composite with well-bonded matrix-reinforcement interfaces, the strength of the matrix would be a dominant element in controlling its properties, as is indicated by the fact that the artificially aged specimens in the present case exhibited a much higher strength and a lower elongation than the NA specimens. And it is widely accepted that any factors which strengthen the matrix would improve the strength of the composite [3-6].

Precipitates, subgrain structures and the thermal mismatch relaxation induced plastic zones around reinforcement particles are the typical examples of such strengthening factors. For a given material condition, lowering testing temperature would result in no essential changes in the precipitation and subgrain microstructures. So, what is left is mainly the thermal mismatch relaxation induced plastic zones generated due to the great difference in the coefficients of thermal expansion between the matrix and the reinforcement. The scale of such plastic zones has been shown to depend strongly on the temperature reduction and the yield strength of the matrix [4,7,8].

In a previous study on the same 6061Al/Al₂O₃ composite [9], we addressed the effect of the enlarged plastic zones on yield strength, by quenching the NA and T6 specimens into liquid nitrogen and then tested at room temperature. It was found that the yield strength of the NA specimens could be enhanced by a factor of 13 percent, while that of the T6 specimens remained unchanged. Considering the much higher enhancement of the yield strength at liquid nitrogen temperature, there must be some other critical factors which have to be taken into account.

In fact, it is well known that cryogenic temperature has the effect of improving mechanical properties of pure Al and most of the age hardenable aluminum alloys without inducing the ductile-to-brittle transition which occurs in many b.c.c. metallic materials [10,11]. The origin of such improvements, though not yet clearly understood, is often attributed to the increase in resistance to dislocation motion, which could be indirectly reflected by the increase in the resistivity ($\Delta\rho$). The latter has been demonstrated to have the following dependence on temperature [12]

$$\Delta\rho = A \exp \{-E_f / k Tq\} \quad (1)$$

where, E_f is the energy of formation of point defects producing the resistivity increase, Tq the absolute quenching temperature, A and k constants. It is also recognized that, for the age hardenable aluminum alloys, as-quenched and naturally aged tempers are more sensitive to the cryogenic strengthening than artificially aged conditions, because of their higher content of point defects. (solute atoms and vacancies) [13]. In addition, it was reported that, with the lowering of testing temperature from 25°C to -196°C, the yield strength of an as-quench 7075 alloy was improved by 28 percent [14]. And when the testing temperature was lowered from room temperature to -184°C, the yield strength and UTS of a 6061-T6 alloy had been improved by 35 and 30 percent respectively [15]. This kind of low temperature-related strengthening would no doubt occur in the 6061Al matrix when the 6061Al/Al₂O₃ composite was deformed at liquid nitrogen temperature, and thus play an important role in improving the cryogenic strength of the composite. Taking this viewpoint into account, the major part of the enhancement in the yield strength of the composite resulted from lowering testing temperature can be reasonably explained.

As the major part of the cryogenic strength improvement of the 6061Al/Al₂O₃ composite can be derived from the low temperature strengthening of its 6061Al matrix, the phenomenon that the artificially aged specimens exhibited a higher elongation along with an improved yield strength at liquid nitrogen temperature also becomes understandable. This is because, it was early known that the concurrent improvement in both the strength and the ductility with lowering testing temperature is a unique behavior of pure Al and its alloys [10], especially those alloys containing light alloying elements like Mg [12] and Li [13]. Other strengthening mechanisms like strain hardening is well known to improve the strength of a material at the expense of a degraded ductility. In view of the above, the markedly enhanced yield strength and the slightly reduced ductility of the NA specimens at liquid nitrogen temperature should be

a net result of the two mechanisms active in the softer 6061Al matrix: (i) the low temperature-related strengthening we discussed here, which could account for the major part of the cryogenic yield strength improvement together with an improved or unaffected ductility; and (ii) the strain hardening originated from the low-temperature-enlarged plastic zones as we demonstrated earlier [9], which would lead to a certain amount of increase in the cryogenic yield strength together with a definitely reduced ductility.

CONCLUSIONS

Conclusions which can be drawn from the present study are as follows: (1) the naturally and artificially aged 6061Al/Al₂O₃ specimens all exhibited obvious strength improvement at liquid nitrogen temperature, (2) the composite exhibited well-bonded matrix-reinforcement interfaces and essentially the same deformation and fracture characteristics at both room and liquid nitrogen temperatures, (3) the enhanced cryogenic elongation and yield strength of the artificially aged specimens are supposed to come from primarily the low temperature-related strengthening of the matrix because of its f.c.c. structure, while the slightly reduced elongation and the markedly improved yield strength of the NA specimens at liquid nitrogen temperature be the net result of both the strain hardening due to the thermal mismatch relaxation induced plastic zones and the low temperature-related strengthening.

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